

REVIEW

on the monograph by Aydin Ali-zade *Communal Services in Azerbaijan in the Mid-20th Century: A Historical-Sociological Study* (translation from Russian)

The monograph submitted for review primarily focuses on the period of the 1950s–1960s but covers a sufficiently wide range of activities, from the organization of management and the foundations of economic activity to science and education within the communal services system of the Azerbaijan SSR. The structure of communal services at that time and the types of activities of enterprises in the field of communal services are described in great detail. The section of the monograph dedicated to the main types of communal services activities—water supply, energy supply, and heating/gas supply—deserves particular attention. The work also addresses the shortcomings of economic activities in the communal services system during that period. The reviewed monograph provides a comprehensive historical analysis of the development of communal services in the Azerbaijan SSR in the mid-20th century and may be of interest to a wide range of researchers studying that period.

Despite the high quality of the materials used in the monograph, the engaging historical overview, and the examination of the establishment and development of communal services in the republic, it is necessary to offer recommendations for the author's further productive work and to note certain shortcomings:

1. The comparison of indicators between enterprises in Moldova and Azerbaijan (pp. 57–59) can hardly be considered representative due to the differing levels of industrial development in the republics.
2. In the section “Plan Implementation,” the reasons for the low level of plan fulfillment in the first halves of the years are not fully explored (pp. 71–80).
3. Although page 194 of the monograph mentions a reduction in morbidity rates in the republic, the topic of the efforts of communal services managers in the field of sanitation remains incompletely addressed. It is recommended that the author, in future work, explore the relationship between improvements in the sanitary-hygienic situation and the reduction in morbidity rates among the population of Azerbaijan during the studied period.

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